

MATERIAL VERSATILITY, LOCALITY AND CHANGE IN CIRCULAR DESIGN

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Introduction

The discipline and practice of architecture is facing a profound dilemma. The pressure on planetary boundaries requires the rethinking of architecture's reliance on CO₂-rich materials and energy-intensive processing. At present, calls envisioning a sustainable building culture focus on renewable and bio-based materials as solutions for carbon neutrality. However, many of these practices carry over industrial paradigms of mass production and standardisation, creating a fundamental reliance on virgin materials and an inability to achieve true cascading. Instead, they intensify the pressure on the ecologies from which materials are cultivated and harvested.

This paper asks how the ideation and prototyping of waste-sourced bio-based materials can drive new models of circularity and reuse in architecture. With a special focus on 3D-printed biopolymer composites, the paper describes the creation of a versatile material system that can respond to local resource availability. Here, the additive logic of 3D printing is extended to support models of functional material grading that can combine variations of the material recipe to create

complex composite architectural panels – first, through strategies of material pleating, and second, through in-process grading.

The paper asks how circularity can challenge models of resource deployment in architecture, and how they might expand the axioms of digital design and fabrication from being driven by models of performance optimisation to incorporating new sensitivities to resource locality.

Local sourcing and variability in the design space
Renewable bio-based resources are categorised as being either first-generation, including food crops and plants; second-generation, including non-edible lignocellulosic biomass or by-products from first-generation production; or third-generation, including algae and food wastes (Bardhan *et al.*, 2015). In the region of southern Scandinavia, where this research is being developed, the landscape is predominantly agricultural. Over centuries it has been optimised to produce high-value biomass focused on food and fuel in the categories of grains, fodder crops, and timber. As a result, the landscape is fully productive and first-generation resources are wholly incorporated into existing material flows. However, the same landscapes and cultivation

practices generate second-generation biomass resources that are not fully utilised. These include wastes and residues including the cut-offs and unused parts of first-generation materials, which are burnt, landfilled or composted, or left to decompose. In general, these biomass resources are seasonally dependent and connected to local agricultural practice and *terroir* (Lucini *et al.*, 2020). Their properties and quantities vary in line with the distinct local environmental and ecological attributes such as soil conditions, micro-environments, and practices of soil conservation. Furthermore, they are sensitive to climatic dynamics including drought, flooding, and disease. Alongside these material streams emerging from cultivated biomass, third-generation streams emerging from uncultivated biomass such as beach-cast seagrass, at present an abundant seasonal resource, can be gathered from coastlines and fjords. As with the first- and second-generation resources described above, the quantity and quality of these third-generation materials are impacted by their local environment and are not consistent.

Beyond this agricultural landscape, anthropogenic wastes such as cotton from linens and clothing are another source for bio-based materials. These materials are sourced through recycling loops. Often the properties of these materials are standardised as a result of industrial processing. However, as they are collected for waste they co-mingle, and the properties of this standardisation need to be carefully sorted in order to be preserved. While this may be possible for certain material streams, it is not feasible for most, making this material resource inherently variable.

First, second, and third-generation materials are part of the circular bio-economy and as such are subject to the same supply and demand dynamics as other resources. At the moment, the circular bio-economy is on a trajectory of rapid development as many industries seek to transfer their production to renewables (Kircher, 2022). This puts additional pressure on the architectural pathways for valorisation of bio-based materials. As new resource loops emerge, previously undervalued materials escalate in value and scarcity. As such, the idealisation of renewables as abundant is ruptured. Instead, we arrive at a resource sensitivity characterised by environmental and ecological dependencies, extreme variability, and changing availability.

These dynamics of resource availability call for new models of material specification and production (Ramsgaard Thomsen and Tamke, 2022) that do not assume the abundance and ready availability of standardised materials, and instead address two

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1. The design composition is generated computationally using a natural growth algorithm called Space Colonization. This algorithm mimics the way that trees and other plants grow in nature, by simulating the growth of branches from a central trunk.

2. *Radicant* is a 3D-printed biopolymer composite interior wall panelling system installed in the Aedes Gallery, Berlin, in 2022. The 26 panels vary in their material composition and are composed of interlacing print beads and differentiated material recipes.

3. *Biopolymer Graded Panels* prototypes an exterior weather screen to assess the opportunities for exterior application of the biopolymer composite, and to monitor the response of different versions of this material to variations in environmental heat and humidity.

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co-dependent criteria: *material variability* – the ability to interchange material constituents in response to local availability – and *material optimisation*, the ability to specify materials in response to design or performance criteria.

A case for designing with resource sensitivity

In our work we explore these resource sensitivities through the case of 3D-printed biopolymer composites. These are explored through the creation of architectural panels for interior and exterior use investigated through two different experiments. In the *Radicant* demonstrator we examine the architectural panel as a retrofitted interior cladding, while in *Biopolymer Graded Panels* we prototype the creation of an exterior weather screen.

In both cases, the panels are developed as deep reliefs with varying material compositions. The panels are 3D printed on a flatbed and the relief is built up through varying layer heights. The print patterns are designed to accelerate the post-printing curing process. The lace-like patterns produce

a high surface to volume ratio, creating a large evaporation surface by which the material can release water content.

Both biopolymer experiments are based on a collagen binder mixed with cellulosic fibres that act as both reinforcements and fillers. Both collagen and fibres are residues of food and agricultural processes. The collagen is bovine, extracted from the meat industry, while the cellulose fibres are derived from various waste streams endemic to our local context. These are bark and wood flour originating from the timber industry, cotton sourced from clothing recycling, and seagrass, a source of blue biomass finding new applications in isolation and packaging.

The collagen biopolymer can become thermoplastic when plasticised with water and polyols (Nicholas *et al.*, 2023a). To achieve a fluid printable state, the material is heated and then mixed. During the 3D-printing process, the temperature of the material is controlled, allowing us precise temperatures at the extrusion head and immediate cooling around the nozzle. This is done through the

making of bespoke robotic extrusion heads combining heating and cooling processes. As part of the fabrication process, the material system undergoes a post-printing state change as it first cools, then cures. As water evaporates during the curing process, the material hardens, becoming resilient and stiff.

The material system is understood as a variable recipe space, which can be adjusted in response to material availability and locality. By mapping multiple recipes against their performance, we challenge the idea of material tuning as the search for a single optimum, instead creating a solution space that can be navigated in response to resource locality and availability providing multiple optima for defined performance criteria. The recipe space can be repeatedly extended and altered, adding new cellulose sources as locality and availability change.

For our studies, the building of the recipe space is based on material testing of strategic recipes spread out across the recipe domain. The tests characterise the strength ratios and elastic modulus of the recipes and allow us to compare the performance of the recipes. The recipes are understood as occupying a dimension mixing different degrees of binder, fibre, and filler sources. The manipulation of the balances within the recipes has direct impact on the resulting material performance. In this way we engage with processes of functional grading enabling the tuning of material composition in response to design-driven performance criteria.

Two approaches for material grading in a variable recipe space

The breadth of the recipe space is used actively in the design of the architectural panels. In the two experiments we create differentiated multi-material print strategies that allow us to deploy varying materials and grade performance. The two strategies are understood as extensions of each other that can be combined, *Radlicant* by strategically pleating the different recipes together in multi-material assemblies, and *Biopolymer Graded Panel* by grading the recipes using a multi-extruder 3D printing head enabling a seamless transition between the recipes. Both strategies are developed by creating an extended digital chain that defines the geometry, details the print path, and steers the material specification of each panel.

Radlicant: Pleating multi-material composites

In *Radlicant* the panels are composed of multiple recipes that are interwoven - or *pleated* together - through a layered design. Pleating the materials results in complex composites that combine different instances of the recipe.

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4. Dog bone samples of differentiated material recipes containing cotton, bark, wood flour, and seagrass fillers. Different fillers impact the mechanical properties of the material. By thinking exploratively rather than towards single-recipe optimisation, we utilise the breadth of this recipe space.

5. In *Radlicant*, the material specifications for each panel respond to the geometry and structural considerations of the design while also incorporating aesthetic considerations. The choice of material, together with the toolpath density, dictates the structural performance stiffness, weight, and visual expression of each panel.

6. In *Biopolymer Graded Panels* the print geometries and material specifications are varied in response to design features, including overhangs, density changes, and connection points, as well as panel-scale grading strategies.

The pleating strategy follows a geometric approach (Nicholas *et al.*, 2023b) and is based on a sequential printing logic. The panel structure is built up in strategic layers that organise the print paths both layer-by-layer and material-by-material, taking into consideration fabrication restraints such as path collision, nozzle spacing, and robot arm placement. The pleating strategy is built up as a structural hierarchy in which base filler layers are followed by a 'trunk structure' and a set of 'branches' that bring an overall assembly-level continuity to the structure.

The 24 panels in *Radlicant* are composed of a total of ten different recipes. These combine the base binder mix, comprising collagen, water, and glycerine, with variant proportions of cellulose sources including bark flower, wood flower, seagrass, and cotton. The choice of fibres affects not only the structural properties of the mix, but also its texture, colour, and finish. For example, glue matrix mixed with 30% wood flour produces a material with 0.7g/cm³ density, 1.35GPa Young's modulus, and a yellow sandy finish, whereas mixing the glue matrix with 30% cotton results in a satin blue material with 3.15GPa Young's modulus, and 1.1g/cm³ density.

The *Radlicant* panels are printed using a robotically steered 3D extrusion process deploying pressure to steer the extrusion. The premixed materials are prepared in extrusion containers that are replaced during the printing process. The heated material achieves the correct viscosity for extrusion at 60°C and integrated heat pads maintain constant print process temperature. The recipe variation affects the rheology of the biopolymer composite. By varying the air pressure, these material changes can be accommodated.

Biopolymer Graded Panels

In *Biopolymer Graded Panels*, we realise continuous grading strategies that seamlessly transition between different recipes of varying viscosity and expression. The specification of grading is achieved through definition of changeover points, where one material flow is enabled and the other is reduced. The grading occurs over the distance of the toolpath, which therefore plays an important role in the legibility and speed of the material transition. *Biopolymer Graded Panels* tests three different grading strategies. In the first, a checkerboard pattern is applied to the panel base in four sections. This strategy maximises the time a material is printed before the switch of material occurs. The second grading strategy splits the base in similar-sized sections. However, instead of alternating the same two material distributions, one of the materials becomes gradually more blended to create a

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gradient that transverses the entire panel. In the third strategy, the grading scheme incrementally increases the time spent printing with each material, creating a single longitudinal gradient throughout the entire panel.

The panels are printed using three recipes. The first is cotton-based, contains 6% cotton fibres by weight, and exhibits a distinctive blue hue. A second material blends 6% bark fibre and 3% cotton fibre to the base biopolymer. The third recipe is wood flour based, and blends 10% wood flour with 1% cotton fibre. In this material, the larger-sized grains are clearly visible.

A custom multiple-feed extruder and feeding system was developed to realise these continuous grading strategies. The design of this system incorporates key considerations regarding material viscosity, temperature control, the mixing of multiple material feeds, the implementation of continuous feeding from a separated reservoir, and the grading control in the fabrication code. The nozzle accepts feeds from two separate pneumatically controlled material feeding reservoirs. Each external reservoir can hold 3l and can be refilled or replaced during the printing process

without introducing inconsistencies or artefacts into the material flow. The extruder is able to grade from one material to another within 3m using a 4mm nozzle.

Conclusion

In this paper we address the potential for bio-based materials to drive new models of circularity and reuse in architecture. If the use of bio-based resources as construction materials is to be intensified as part of a sustainable building culture, there is a need to diversify the materials used, and to localise their sourcing. Where virgin and first-generation materials are already fully utilised in regions such as ours, new design and fabrication pathways for second and third-generation-based biomaterials need to be created. To be flexible, these should be grounded in an appreciation of the locality and accessibility of resources, as well as the variability of quantity and quality that is inherent to second and third-generation biomass. These considerations present a new dynamic in resource flow that challenges modern assumptions of abundant and standardised materials.

7 & 8. Detailed view of the grading achieved during the printing process. The density of toolpath geometries plays an important role in the legibility of the material transition, with grading occurring more quickly in areas of high density.

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We have grounded our exploration in two cases that demonstrate interior and exterior applications for 3D-printed biopolymer composite panels. The biopolymer composite is developed to be flexible to the changing availability of waste streams and supports a variable recipe space through the ability to vary and interchange constituent materials. The *Radical* and *Biopolymer Graded Panels* cases demonstrate how this is operationalised through printing strategies, specifically pleating and continuous grading, which tune the material composition in response to design-driven performance criteria.

The projects ask how architecture can expand its methodologies to incorporate fresh ideas of the grown and the harvested. It questions the axiom of abundance, instead presenting new methods that extend existing paradigms of material optimisation to incorporate ideas of material substitution to be able to resiliently adapt to changes in resource availability as material flows fluctuate in the circular bio-economy.

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